

MEMORANDUM

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TO: THE CLERK TO THE COMMITTEE
COMMITTEE ON CONSTITUTIONAL, LEGAL & PARLIAMENTARY AFFAIRS
OFFICE OF PARLIAMENT
ACCRA

DATE: OCTOBER 7, 2021

SUBJECT: PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND GHANAIAN FAMILY
VALUES BILL, 2021

1. Introduction

I want to be clear from the outset that I am not against homosexuals. As a Christian counselor and patron of the University Christian Fellowship (UCF), the coordinating body of all Christian groups on the University of Ghana campus, I have come to know a number of students who were struggling with their sexual identity. Most of them are good people who needed compassion, salvation and repentance and guidance and counseling. To such homosexuals, we must always speak in love, and never in hatred. But the first task of love is to tell the truth, even if the truth hurts. I have seen lives genuinely liberated, reformed and transformed by the gospel of Jesus Christ as the sole and sufficient Saviour. These life encounters have given me a better appreciation of what we are confronted with as a nation.

As a Christian I am deeply troubled by the avalanche of immorality that threatens to inundate this nation of my nativity. I have had the benefit of reading the many opinions of informed and uninformed, uneducated and learned personalities on the subject of same-sex relationships and the calls for tolerance, on the one hand, and criminalization, on the other hand, in Ghana. I find it expedient and indeed very compelling that since these issues affect the soul and destiny of this country in its democratic sojourn, it is important to add my own critical views in these few words. This is because I consider the issues germane to this debate as having the potential of determining the path which this country should tread, whether it should be the dreadful path of criminalizing the practice or a liberal society without the vestiges of regulation as unfortunately has been introduced in some western countries. Let us be honest. There is apparent decline in morality in the western countries today. Many of those countries are hemorrhaging. Families are falling apart.

Nothing illustrates the tragedy of the world we live in today better than the radical transformation of our society's sexual ethics, which has come in direct contradistinction to the teaching of Scripture and to the cultural standards that have made Western Civilization what it is. Until recently, no society had seen marriage as anything other than a conjugal partnership between a male and a female (a man and his wife).

I have followed closely the discourses written upon the subject and hereby submit this memorandum to draw your attention to some concerns, especially in light of the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 (“the Bill”). I offer these educated thoughts in the hope that they may add to our knowledge of these vexed issues and help to draw attention to—and offer some insight about the LGBT challenge facing many countries now. In doing so, I have tried very hard to be candid, direct and honest.

2. Some Major Scientific Misconceptions

A recent report¹ authored by Dr. Lawrence S. Mayer, an epidemiologist trained in psychiatry, and a professor of statistics and biostatistics at Arizona State University and Dr. Paul R. McHugh, a professor of psychiatry and behavioral sciences at the Johns Hopkins University School of Medicine, for twenty-five years the psychiatrist-in-chief at the Johns Hopkins Hospital, one of the leading psychiatrists in the world, and arguably the most important American psychiatrist of the last half-century, examining research from the biological, psychological, and social sciences, has incontrovertibly shown that some of the most frequently heard claims about sexuality and gender are not supported by any credible scientific evidence.

- *Sexual Orientation: Are People Lesbians, Gays & Bisexuals?*

There is a widely held view that *sexual orientation* is innate and fixed in each person—as it is often put, gay people are “born that way”. Professors Mayer and McHugh offer a careful summary and an up-to-date explanation of many of the most rigorous findings produced by the biological, psychological, and social sciences related to sexual orientation and gender identity. After examining a vast body of scientific literature from several disciplines, including epidemiology, genetics, endocrinology, psychiatry, neuroscience, embryology, pediatrics, psychology, sociology, political science, economics, and gender studies, they found no credible scientific evidence for the view that sexual orientation is a fixed and innate biological property. That is to say that, the most commonly accepted view in popular discourse within the lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) community—the “born that way” notion that homosexuality and heterosexuality are biologically innate or the product of very early developmental factors—is not a view that is well-supported by research (Mayer & McHugh, 2016). These findings are consistent with the current state of science on gender and sexual orientation. For example, the largest study

¹ Mayer, L. S. and McHugh, P. R. (2016). Sexuality and Gender: Findings from the Biological, Psychological, and Social Sciences. *The New Atlantis: A Journal of Technology and Society, Special Report No. 50*. https://www.thenewatlantis.com/wp-content/uploads/legacy-pdfs/20160819_TNA50SexualityandGender.pdf

to date on the genetic basis of sexuality has revealed that there is no genetic basis for human sexuality (Ganna et al, 2019 cited in Lambert, 2019). “There is no ‘gay gene’,” says lead study author Andrea Ganna, a geneticist at the Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard in Cambridge, Massachusetts.²

- *Gender Identity*

Another emerging and related misinformation being advanced by the LGBT community and its advocates is the view that *gender identity*—the subjective, internal sense of being a man or a woman (or some other gender category)—is also fixed at birth or at a very early age and can diverge from a person’s biological sex. This is sometimes articulated by saying that a boy may be trapped in a girl’s body, or vice versa. Again, professors Mayer and McHugh argue in their study that there is little scientific evidence that *gender identity* is fixed at birth or at an early age. In reviewing the scientific literature, they find that almost nothing is well understood when we seek biological explanations for what causes some individuals to state that their gender does not match their biological sex. Yet despite the scientific uncertainty, the professors worry that drastic interventions are prescribed and delivered to patients identifying, or identified, as *transgender*, including medical and surgical interventions for many prepubescent children, some as young as six, and other therapeutic approaches undertaken for children as young as two (Mayer & McHugh, 2016).

The implication of the above findings is that, it is not true that people are born gays; sexual orientation is neither innate nor fixed in each person; no one is born transgender; people are born male or female. This means that the whole argument of sexual minority collapses right on its head. LGBTQ+ is just a preference, it’s a voluntary lifestyle choice, not different from polygamy or adultery. It is interesting that till today, several states in the USA and other western nations have laws criminalizing polygamy.

3. Constitutional Arguments

It is true that Ghana is a democracy. Good democratic governance is the bedrock of economic growth and sustainable human development. However, true democracy entails moral, ethical and cultural uprightness. Perhaps the most familiar conception of the role of democracy is that it serves as the means whereby a people as a whole asserts its collective will: its own will as distinct from the will of a dictator or an elite or a foreign power. On this conception, democracy is an ideal for a people that parallels the ideal of autonomy for an individual. The democratic people is an autonomous people: a people which gives laws to itself, rather than have them emanate from an alien or heteronomous source.³

² Lambert, J. (2019). No ‘Gay Gene’: Study Looks at Genetic Basis for Human Sexuality. *Nature*, Vol. 573, 5 September 3019. <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-02585-6> (Accessed 30 September 2021).

³ Petit Philip (2004). Depoliticizing Democracy. *Ratio Juris*. Vol. 17 No. 1, pp. 52–65.

Democracy without morality is anarchy. The State has a duty and responsibility to promote good governance, which include protecting public morality, ethics and cultural uprightness. This duty of the State includes controlling deviance. It is the highest order of irresponsibility for the State to sit down for the moral ecology of the nation to be destroyed by a few self-seeking individuals. Morality is a public good which must be provided and protected by any responsible State.

I have heard some intellectuals argue that Ghana is a secular democratic republic, whatever that means. It is important to understand what these people mean by such statements. In what sense can this country be called a *secular* country? A basic definition of secularity is: “the state of being unrelated or neutral in regards to religion or spirituality”. I find this description of Ghana quite perplexing and intellectually dishonest, especially when such statements are being loudly trumpeted by pro-LGBTQ+ intellectuals, lawyers included. Such a claim is neither consistent with reality nor is it supported by the Constitution of the Republic of Ghana, both in its letter and spirit.

Indeed, the preamble of the Constitution of the Republic of Ghana says: “THE CONSTITUTION OF THE REPUBLIC OF GHANA 1992, IN THE NAME OF THE ALMIGHTY GOD...” Undoubtedly, the framers of the 1992 Constitution recognized that Ghana is a religious democratic country with an overwhelming Christian majority. Truly, Ghana is a nation whose God is THE ALMIGHTY GOD (Psalm 33:12), in whose name its Constitution is promulgated. It is evident to any visitor to Ghana that faith and religion play a critical role in the socio-political life of our nation and always have, and the church has had a strong influence on the state, and this has worked to our benefit as a nation. The national anthem and national pledge are not secular. They are invocations of the blessings of the Almighty God on our homeland Ghana. Contrary to what some people think, those who created our country - the founding fathers and mothers - understood that there is a divine order which transcends the human order. Our governments were not intended to be purely secular. The vast majority of Ghanaians believe in the God of creation; Christian (more than 72% of the population) and Islamic (more than 17 percent of the population) influences are universal. In fact, some people may not like to admit it, but like it or not, Ghana is a highly religious country.

Essential to understanding *secularism* is the recognition that in modern culture, there is a consistent line of secular humanists activism is determined to overthrow the cultural dominance of Christianity. Advocates of LGBTQ+ have been quite clear and explicit that they see Christianity as a harmful encumbrance on society. They are asking the world to abandon the Judeo-Christian worldview in favour of the attitudes of contemporary European and American life – feminism, multiculturalism, gay liberationism, and lifestyle liberalism, accompanied by abortion, euthanasia, embryonic stem cell experimentation, and the rest of the culture of death (Hindson and Caner, 2008).⁴ All leading secular humanists, including Richard Dawkins and Christopher Hitchens, are cultural radical atheists. The Christians and Moslems, indeed, the religious people of Ghana are saying that any attempt by the few

⁴ Hindson, E. and Caner, E. (2008). *The Popular Encyclopedia of Apologetics: Surveying the Evidence for the Truth of Christianity*. Harvest House Publishers.

secular humanists to push for the rejection of the values, morals, and standards that define the Ghanaian culture in favour of an agenda of moral relativism, militant secularism, and sexual and social liberation, will be forcefully and lawfully resisted.

Homosexuality as a Deviance Behaviour

Sociologists define “deviant” behavior or “deviance” as *acts, beliefs, and characteristics that violate major social norms and attract, or are likely to attract, condemnation, stigma, social isolation, censure, and/or punishment by relevant audiences* (Clinard, 1957, p. vii; Clinard & Meier, 2011; cited in Goode, 2015:4).

Every country has its histories, values, and cultures that inform what is acceptable and tolerable. According to Erich Goode, Sociology Professor Emeritus,

“Virtually all societies everywhere and throughout recorded time have established and promulgated rules or *norms* – including codified laws – that demarcate the good from the bad: the true from the false, desirable from undesirable, acceptable from unacceptable, legal from illegal, licit from illicit, legitimate from illegitimate, and behavior, beliefs, and characteristics that are valued from those that are disvalued. Likewise, all societies have spelled out sanctions, punishments – appropriate reactions that audiences and agents of social control should invoke or apply against violators of those rules. And all societies invoke such sanctions against miscreants variably according to the nature of the violation – its degree of seriousness and whether it is the breach of formal or informal norms, whether it becomes widely known, what the circumstances of the violation are, and who the violators are – for instance, their age, social rank, and their degree of intimacy with relevant audiences”.⁵

It is no wonder, therefore, that the Republic of Ghana Criminal Offences Act of 1960 (Act 29), Article 104(1) of Chapter 6, makes the practice of homosexuality amongst men a criminal offence in Ghana by providing that a person who has unnatural carnal knowledge of another person of not less than sixteen years of age with the consent of that other person commits a misdemeanor.⁶ Such a law is “reasonably necessary”. Truly, it is commonsensical, to the extent that it seeks to protect public morality and public health. Such a law is consistent with the aspirations of the people of Ghana.

⁵ Goode, E. (2015:3). *The Sociology of Deviance: An Introduction*, Ch. 1 in Goode, 2015, *Handbook of Deviance*. WILEY Blackwell.

⁶ Unnatural carnal knowledge, as defined at common law, involves penile penetration of anything other than a vagina. By this definition, the law only anticipates the situation where a man has unnatural carnal knowledge of a woman or another man, but does not envisage the situation where a woman engages in unnatural carnal knowledge of another woman (lesbianism), and this lacuna in the law is what the Bill seeks to cure.

Just last month, the state of New York in the United States of America, for example, passed a new law that bans the sale of gas vehicles starting in 2035, requiring all new cars to be zero emission. New York's Senate and Assembly passed the bill and Governor Kathy Hochul signed it into law. In 14 years' time, no fossil fuel-powered vehicles will be sold in New York anymore. The move is aimed at helping reduce the state's greenhouse gas emissions by 35 percent and help it achieve its climate targets, including an 85 percent reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2050. In the last one year, the states of California and Massachusetts passed new regulations that banned the sales of new gas-powered cars by 2035.⁷ This decision by governments of the States of New York, California and Massachusetts will definitely infringe on the rights, preferences and choices of a good number of Americans who love to exercise their right to choose to drive a fossil fuel-powered vehicles but the common good is what is being promoted and protected by these laws. Nevertheless, in the wisdom of the government, such laws are necessary for the common good.

As per the various surveys so far undertaken in Ghana, including the Afrobarometer (“let the people have a say”) surveys,⁸ which are administered by the Ghana Center for Democratic Development (CDD), it is obvious that Ghanaians are united against homosexuality in Ghana. It is profoundly revealing to find that an overwhelming majority of Ghanaians, from across different socio-demographic groups, reject entertaining people who identify as and LGBTQ+ person as a neighbor, both in the community and at the work place.

What are the People of Ghana Saying about LGBTQ+?

In 2014, 9 out of 10 Ghanaians (89%) said they would “somewhat dislike” or “strongly dislike” living next door to people in same-sex relationships. Only 11% would not care or would like having such individuals as neighbours (Figure 1). By 2019, “dislike/strongly dislike” for having homosexual neighbours had increased to 93% (way above the African average of 80%), indicating a still growing unacceptance of homosexuality in Ghana (see Figures 2 & 3).⁹

⁷ <https://www.engadget.com/california-to-ban-sale-of-new-gaspowered-cars-by-2035-180313529.html> (Accessed on October 7, 2021).

⁸ The Afrobarometer’s website boasts of being the world’s leading source of high-quality data on what Africans are thinking. So, the above findings represent what ordinary Ghanaians are thinking. Ghanaians have had their say and it is palpably very clear in the minds of Ghanaians that same-sex relationships are unacceptable.

⁹ In 2019, the Afrobarometer survey used the term “homosexual” to represent the broader category of LGBTQ+ persons.

Figure 1: Rejection of LGBTQ+ lifestyles in Ghana, 2014

Source: Afrobarometer survey

Figure 2: Rejection of Homosexuality in Ghana, 2019

Source: Afrobarometer survey 2019

Figure 3: Dislike of Homosexuality in 23 African Countries, 2019/2020

Source: Afrobarometer survey 2019/2020

Rejection of people in same-sex relationships is widespread, across age groups, educational background, religious affiliations, and urban as well as rural locations (see Figure 4 & Table 1). Even among the most educated in Ghanaian society, including the lawyers, parliamentarians, judges, medical doctors, and academics, an overwhelming 86 percent of them expressed a dislike living with a homosexual person as a neighbor. It is even striking to find that 88 percent of Ghanaians indicated that they “dislike/strongly dislike” having an LGBTQ+ person as a co-worker. This is a very grim finding. What does this mean. It means, for example, that almost 9 in 10 parliamentarians would not like to sit in the same chamber with a colleague member of parliament who identifies as an LGBTQ+ person. Nearly 9 out of 10 judges abhors the thought of sitting at the bar with a colleague judge who is a homosexual, on top of the fact that they would not like to live with such persons in the same estates or neighborhood. This is a national paranoia. It is also very revealing to find that contrary to what the LGBTQ+ advocates would have the world believe that religiosity, especially Christianity, is the main driver of intolerance of persons in same-sex relationships, the Afrobarometer survey indicate that the abhorrence of homosexual behavior in Ghana is pervasive across even people who identify with “other religion or none” – at least 8 in 10 non-Christian/non-Muslim Ghanaians reject having people in same-sex relationships as a neighbor or co-worker (See Figure 4 & Table 1).

Figure 4: Rejection of people in same-sex relationship by socio-demographic group, 2014

Source: Afrobarometer survey 2014

Table 1: Rejection of people in same-sex relationship in the work place, 2014

		As Co-Worker	As Supervisor
Religion	Other Religion or None	83%	83%
	Christian	88%	88%
	Muslim	90%	90%
Education	Tertiary	78%	79%
	Secondary	84%	83%
	Primary	89%	90%
	No Formal Education	93%	93%
Age	Elderly (61 years or more)	92%	90%
	Older Adults (50-60 years)	90%	91%
	Young Adults (36-49 years)	90%	89%
	Youth (18-35 years)	86%	86%
Gender	Women	90%	90%
	Men	86%	86%
Settlement Type	Rural	92%	92%
	Urban	85%	85%
National Average		88%	88%

Source: Afrobarometer survey 2014

One policy implication of these findings is that the continuous importation of LGBTQ+ lifestyle into Ghana poses a threat to communal values and social cohesion in Ghana. The continuous promotion of homosexual behavior is already heightening tensions between communal and individualistic values in several communities. This is a security issue that we must all be wary of. It is not surprising therefore that an overwhelming majority (at least 85%) of Ghanaians said they would be inclined to report their own children – as well as other relatives and friends – or co-workers to the police or other authorities if they discovered that they were in same-sex relationships (see Figure 5). This means, nearly 9 in 10 Ghanaian fathers/mothers would prefer to have their own sons/daughters arrested by the police if they discovered that they were indulging in same-sex relationships. It means that such parents do not believe or accept the explanation that same-sex relationship is a human right issue. Ghanaians see homosexuality more as a deviance that must not be countenanced anywhere in the society, be it at home, school, work place, or neighborhood.

Figure 5: Reporting persons in same-sex relationship to police or authorities, 2014

Source: Afrobarometer survey 2014

Without doubt, the Afrobarometer surveys have proved that Ghana is a liberal country, a country of tolerance, a multicultural, pluralistic country. However, it is apparent that the overwhelming majority of Ghanaians see homosexuality as a deviance behavior, and would wish to have it legally proscribed by relevant institutions, beginning with the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs. An overwhelming majority (86%) of Ghanaians have said they would approve of a decision by government to criminalize same-sex relationships (Figure 6). Only about one in ten Ghanaians said they would oppose such a law (Figure 5). I know you would have received some strong memoranda from some groups belonging this minority, who are asking for tolerance and inclusivity. Unfortunately, Ghanaians have shown to be among the most tolerant people in the world. But on this particular matter of LGBT ideology, the loud calls for tolerance have clearly been rejected, since it is wrong that we are being asked to tolerate.

Figure 6: Support for Legislation Criminalising Same-Sex Relationships - Ghana 2014

Source: Afrobarometer survey 2014.

Note: Respondents were asked: If government decides to pass a law making same-sex relationships illegal in the country, would you approve or disapprove of it?

The foregoing statistics reflected in the work by Ghana’s Constitution Review Commission (CRC), established in 2010 to collate public opinion on aspects of the 1992 Constitution, which indicated that more than 98 percent of public comments it received on the subject opposed legalizing same-sex relationships (see Republic of Ghana, 2011).¹⁰ Perhaps quite shockingly, the CRC did not see the need in adding explicit constitutional provisions outlawing same-sex relationships on the grounds that they would be considered reactionary and unworthy of a progressive state. The Commission says that: “a suggestion to introduce a provision in the Constitution expressly excluding same-sex marriages in Ghana would be clearly seen by many people in the country and outside of it as a reactionary move not worthy of a progressive state.” Unfortunately, the Commission left people like me wondering what it meant by “progressive state”. Is the Commission suggesting America became a “progressive state” because it legalized same-sex marriage in all fifty states in 2015? Or, has Switzerland only become a “progressive state” in September 2021 after voting to legalize same-sex marriage? Another challenge I have with the Commission’s conclusion on this matter is the suggestion that if same-sex relationship was to be proscribed by the Constitution, “many people in the country and outside of it” would see it as unworthy. I guess the “many” people are non-Ghanaians. The evidence from the Afrobarometer surveys (Figures 1-6 & Table 1) and the public comments received by the CRC clearly supports the view that an overwhelming majority of Ghanaians favour of the non-recognition of the right to sexual orientation for homosexuals in Ghana. In the final analysis, the CRC recommended that the decision on whether or not

¹⁰ Republic of Ghana. (2011). Report of the constitutional review commission: From a political to a developmental constitution. (pp. 654-657).

to legalize same-sex relationships or not should be left in abeyance until the matter gets to the Supreme Court.

I am inclined to question the value of such recommendation. This singular recommendation leaves much to be desired. To my mind, I think the Commission could have given a clearer direction on what future the government must chart, on the basis of the evidence that came before it. The vague recommendation left the President with no choice than to leave the matter in the shadows. In its white paper on the CRC's report (Republic of Ghana, 2012), the government "took note" of the commission's recommendation. That is all the White Paper said about such a contentious and passion-inflaming issue.

I know very well that laws do not necessarily make men moral but laws such as the Bill envisages can contribute to the sustenance of moral character in two ways. Most obviously, while the law cannot obliterate LGBTQ+ from Ghana, it can make LGBTQ+ practices less plentiful or less extreme or less obtrusive, thereby promoting a social environment more conducive to the conduct of moral education by those most directly involved. Secondly, the law can educate, in a less obvious but far-reaching manner, through its stigmatization of homosexual behaviour, thereby reaffirming the threatened ethical standard and endorsing moral opinion. It is important to note that the social welfare has a moral as well as a material component. Therefore, the right and duty of the government to maintain a decent society cannot be overemphasized.

Other Constitutional Arguments

The Constitution of the Republic of Ghana, Article 1, Section 1, says: "The Sovereignty of Ghana resides in the people of Ghana in whose name and for whose welfare the powers of government are to be exercised in the manner and within the limits laid down in the Constitution." The powers of government must be exercised in the name and for the welfare of the people of Ghana, not some foreign institutions and nations, be it the United Nations. To ignore the over 90 percent of Ghanaians who have expressed their abhorrence to homosexuality and pander to intimidation by foreign countries and institutions is not a secure and an ideal democracy. The will of the majority must be respected. If Ghana was a well-developed democracy, this would not have been a matter for debate any longer. The UK voted to leave the EU (Brexit) by a mere 52 percent majority. Switzerland voted on 26th September to approve same-sex marriage in a nationwide referendum with a just about 64 percent of voters in favour. It is clear that the people of Ghana do not want homosexuality and it would be an injustice and serious misgovernment to subvert the will of the majority. In fact, the way I see it, it is like the whole nation is 'sitting on a time bomb' waiting to explode. It is a security challenge that needs to be handled with wisdom. As the people's elected representative, it must be seen that you are representing their interests and aspirations. Anything short of this would be a great disappointment and betrayal of trust. This would be what we call in economics the "principal-agent problem, which arises when there is a conflict of interest between the agent and the principal resulting in the agent acting solely in his/her own interests. The principal is the party (in this case your constituents) that legally appoints the agent (in this case the parliamentarians) to make decisions and take actions on its

behalf. This relationship comes with rewards and punishments. Please, I urge you to keep your eyes on the 2024 general elections. Otherwise, your own continuous existence as legislators could be in danger.

Further, Article 37, Section 4, of the Constitution of Ghana says: “The State shall maintain a population policy consistent with the aspirations and development needs and objectives of Ghana.” Homosexuality is not a strategic and sustainable population policy and it is not consistent with the aspirations and development needs and objectives of Ghana – it will lead to a substantial loss in population. The specter of depopulation is already haunting some western countries. Some policy analysts fear that if the fertility rates in the United States and Europe remain as low as they currently are, the security of these nations may be jeopardized and its cultural influence undermined.¹¹ As a sovereign nation, we should not follow their dangerous path that threatens our very existence in the long term.

Article 26, Section 2, of the Constitution of Ghana says: “All customary practices which dehumanise or are injurious to the physical and mental well-being of a person are prohibited.” In addition, Article 39, Section 2, of the same Constitution says: “The State shall ensure that appropriate customary and cultural values are adapted and developed as an integral part of the growing needs of the society as a whole; and in particular that traditional practices which are injurious to the health and well-being of the person are abolished.” On the basis of these two constitutional provisions, I wish to submit that homosexuality, as I have come to understand it, is a dehumanizing practice that is injurious to both the physical and mental well-being of the homosexuals themselves and to public health in general and must therefore be legally prohibited.

The Constitution of the Republic of Ghana, Article 36, Section 1, says: “The State shall take all necessary action to ensure that the national economy is managed in such a manner as to maximize the rate of economic development and to secure the maximum welfare, freedom and happiness of every person in Ghana and to provide adequate means of livelihood and suitable employment and public assistance to the needy.” As a development economist with substantial experience globalization and poverty, I can say without any equivocation that no single industrialized nation countenanced this liberal ideology in their early stages of development. It is just too costly and economically unwise as a nation still struggling to be a ‘Ghana without aid’ to go down this path. Economic development will not be maximized in a situation where we promote lifestyles that are clearly injurious to the public health and public purse. We simply do not have the fiscal space to support the economic and social costs of such liberties and lifestyles.

The Constitution of the Republic of Ghana, Article 40 (a) says: “In its dealings with other nations, the Government shall promote and protect the interests of Ghana”. While we wish to adhere to the UN and other international laws, the interest of Ghana must be paramount to Government. Unless we are all a bunch of hypocrites, it is palpably clear that homosexual behavior is not in the interests of Ghana. Most Ghanaians think that homosexuality is morally undesirable and does not serve our common good—it

¹¹ C. Alison McIntosh and Barbara B. Crane (1986). Population Decline: A Threat to the West?. *Family Planning Perspectives*, Vol. 18, No. 5, pp. 234-238.

offends against a range of aspirational ideals, religious and otherwise. Allowing homosexuality to continue in the Ghanaian society, thereby giving it a sort of state recognition and acceptance, will be a typical case in which *cultural imperialism* rules, in place of the considerations of the common Ghanaian good. Such a decision will be untenable in a country like ours where a clear overwhelming majority, religious or otherwise, learned or unlearned, male or female, have expressed their unwillingness to tolerate homosexual behavior as a way of life. Unless this Government exists purely to serve the interest of the United Nations and the now industrialized and rich countries, the LGBT movement must be lawfully curtailed.

The Constitution of the Republic of Ghana, Article 17, Section 2, says: “A person shall not be discriminated against on grounds of gender, race, colour, ethnic origin, religion, creed or social or economic status.” I have heard some prominent homosexual advocates, including some leading legal minds, argue the instant bill before parliament is discriminatory on the basis of this constitutional provision. However, the bill before parliament is more about what homosexuals *do* rather than who they *are*. Moreover, gender, as envisioned by the framers of the 1992 Constitution, is what accords with the social and cultural context of Ghana, which this Bill seeks to uphold. I have never seen a single national document, be it passport, birth certificate, driver’s license, NHIS card, Ghana card, where sex or gender is defined to mean anything else than male and female. Neither have I seen a single national survey, be it Ghana Population Census, Ghana Living Standards Survey (GLSS), Ghana Multiple Indicator Survey (MICS), Ghana Demographic and Health Survey (GDHS), that has LGBTQ+ as an alternative gender or marital status. This is manifest evidence that LGBTQ+ has never been part of the Ghanaian cultural values and social norms. Indeed, the concept of *sexual orientation* was a recent intentional and quite successful attempt to redefine the cultural debate over homosexuality from same-sex sexual acts to homosexual identity – that is, from what homosexuals *do* to who homosexuals *are*. In fact, until recently, the concept more employed by the homosexual movement was *sexual preference*. The reason for the shift is obviously tactical: “preference” implied a voluntary choice, so the clinical category of “orientation” was more appealing in public arguments.

The Potential Constitutional Implications of LGBTQ+ Agenda

Homosexuality is not a new subject. This world is old and we have the experience of about six thousand years to guide us make wise policy choices. It is important to understand how homosexual movement came upon us, its history, politics and propaganda, and agenda. Winston Churchill once said that, “The greatest advances in human civilization have come when we recovered what we had lost: when we learned the lessons of history.”¹²

Western culture has now been moving away from its Christian values since the *Renaissance* and the *Enlightenment*. Hence *secularism* has gradually and aggressively replaced Christianity as the dominant

¹² See George Grant & Mark Horne (1991:43). *Unnatural Affections: The Impuritan Ethic of Homosexuality and the Modern Church*. Legacy Press. Franklin, Tennessee.

Western philosophy. The origins of the homosexual movement as a major cultural force is traced to the 1969 Stonewall riots in Manhattan, New York. What followed was a measured and strategic effort (1) to win the legitimization of homosexuality, (2) to promote homosexual themes in the media, and (3) to receive special recognition for homosexuals as a legally protected class (Hindson and Caner, 2008). Furthermore, the movement has pushed for specific policy goals, such as the removal of all anti-sodomy laws, the recognition of homosexual partnerships on par with heterosexual marriage, and the enactment of anti-discrimination laws.

This agenda and *modus operandi* of the homosexual movement can be seen in the West's experiences with the rights of LGBTQ+ persons. Until the mid-20th century, same-sex intimate relationships long had been condemned as immoral by the state itself in most Western nations, a belief often embodied in the criminal law. For much of the 20th century, moreover, homosexuality was treated as an illness. And in mainstream America, homosexuality had always been considered socially wrongful or deviant until recently. Currently in American society the status of homosexuality is still evolving – still deviant, though less so over time. When the *American Psychiatric Association* published the first *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* in 1952, homosexuality was classified as a mental disorder, a position adhered to until 1973. It is only recently that psychiatrists and others have recognized that sexual orientation is both a normal expression of human sexuality and immutable. In recent years, the homosexual movement has lobbied global institutions and mental health organizations to have homosexuality removed from the list of classified diagnostic pathologies, and many have come to see it as nothing more than a morally neutral personal preference or a naturally occurring aspect of human biological diversity. Furthermore, the homosexual movement has successfully relied on liberal values of *equality* and *autonomy* to advance the rights of homosexuals in the West. The new argument is that homosexuals exist as a special minority class – a “third sex” alongside heterosexual men and women and must be accorded equal rights. This is how the homosexual movement managed to tactically literally ‘force’ the American Psychiatric Association to remove homosexuality from the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Psychiatric Disorders* in 1973.

Indeed, the goal of the homosexual liberation movement is not merely the legitimization of homosexual activity or even the recognition of homosexual relationships. As if that was not enough, the movement has succeeded in pushing for the full entrenchment of liberal ideology in international law, and the language of constitutions of countries across the industrialized countries and a growing number of emerging economies reflects the influence of liberal philosophy. The agenda of the homosexual movement is the creation of a public homosexual culture in the whole new LGBTQ+ world that seeks to control the whole world system and ideologies and obliterate heterosexual culture and take even our rights and force us to eat what we do not like.

I have read and listened to many of the discourses on the pros and cons of the instant bill before parliament. What is clearly missing from the arguments being advanced by the pro-homosexual (against the bill) group is the broader agenda and implication of the homosexual movement in Ghana as can be observed from the West. In countries where LGBTQ+ has been legalized, it has affected almost every aspect of economic,

social, and cultural life – from public health to public morality, government spending, education, business and religious freedom, to name but a few. For the first time since the fourth century, the Christian church is once again facing persecution in America and Europe – there are major cases the courts on conflict between gay and religious rights.

For example, in an article by Lawrence Hurley of Washington-based Reuters News Agency, posted on March 18, 2019, the U.S. Supreme Court handed down a defeat to a bed and breakfast owner in Hawaii, Phyllis Young, for allegedly turning away a lesbian couple due to her Christian beliefs. The justices upheld a lower court’s ruling that she violated a Hawaii anti-discrimination law by refusing to rent a room to the lesbian couple Diane Cervilli and Taeko Bufford in 2007. A state court ruled that Young ran afoul of Hawaii’s public accommodation law, which among other things bars discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation. Young, who is Catholic, argued that her decision to turn away the lesbian couple was protected by her right to free exercise of religion under the U.S. Constitution’s First Amendment.¹³

Recently, a 44 year old mother was sacked from her job as a school assistant after flagging up concerns of the teaching of LGBTQ+ rights in a school where his son attends. Firms have been sued in court for refusing to offer their services to homosexuals because it is against their faith and belief. The homosexual movement is currently advocating the teaching of LGBQ+ as a subject in primary and secondary schools in countries that have accepted this new paradigm. They seek to bring gender pronouns that will capture their confusion and seek to remove/add to commonly used pronouns like he, she, his and her. They are even seeking to remove the titles “mother” and “father” and replace them with “parent” to suit gay couples who have adopted children.

There is presently in America, a confusion about the use of public bathrooms according to one’s preferred sexual orientation, not the sex assigned by birth. There are also problems with prison inmates being mixed together – women prisoners sharing the same ward with men who now claim to be female. Recently, the Republican governor, Tate Reeves, had to sign a bill requiring the state’s schools to designate teams by sex assigned at birth, saying it would “protect young girls from being forced to compete with biological males for athletic opportunities.” The argument is that transgender girls, because they were born male, are naturally stronger, faster and bigger than those born female. Opponents of the bill say such proposals violate federal education law prohibiting sex discrimination as well as rulings by the United States Supreme Court.

In a bizarre misgendering case, the British Columbia Human Rights Tribunal ruled in favor of Jessie Nelson, a restaurant worker who had filed a complaint against their former employer, Buono Osteria. Nelson, who is nonbinary and genderfluid, claimed the boss discriminated against them by intentionally using incorrect pronouns. In a 42-page ruling, Tribunal found that the restaurant’s alleged misconduct violated British Columbia’s Human Rights Act. The court was of the view that pronouns are “a fundamental part of a person’s identity” and that their proper usage indicates “that we see and respect a

¹³ <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-usa-court-lgbt-idUSKCN1QZ1LK> (Accessed on October 7, 2021).

person for who they are.” “Especially for trans, non-binary, or other non-cisgender people, using the correct pronouns validates and affirms they are a person equally deserving of respect and dignity.”¹⁴

In a related transgender case, the Supreme Court of British Columbia, Canada, has ruled in favour of a teenager who wants medical treatment in his gender transition, despite the opposition of his father. The ruling means that the teenager can start hormone therapy even though his father thinks he is not mature enough to make such a decision.¹⁵ Such rulings that seek to grant transgender kids more legal rights and protections without the consent of their parents are becoming ubiquitous in North America and Europe.

In another LGBTQ+ case, Byron Cross, a physical education teacher at Leesburg Elementary School, Loudoun County, Virginia, was placed on leave days after he spoke out against a proposed school policy that says educators should refer to students by the pronouns that align with their preferred gender identity. He had told the school board that following the proposed policy would go against his religious beliefs.¹⁶

I could go on and on and on with facts and figures and if necessary real life stories of the peril of the homosexual culture. With all the evidence that abounds about the destructiveness of this harmful ideology, I shudder to contemplate that any sage leader would wish to take Ghana down this slippery path. We should not follow the multitude in wrongdoing (Exodus 23:2). We should not consent to those sinners who seek to entice us to follow them in this broad way that leads to destruction, even if those who enter by it claim to be more enlightened than us (Proverbs 1:10; Mathew 7:13-14).

The Akans have some proverbs that may be applicable:

“Abaa a wɔde bɔɔ Takyi no, wɔde bɛbɔ Baah dabi”, to *wit*, the same rod used to punish Takyi will be used on Baah for committing the same offence.

“Dua a Ananse adi awuo, Ntikuma nkɔtena aseɛ nto nko”, to *wit*, one does not sit and slumber under the tree which killed his Father.

4. Law, Culture and Public Morality Arguments

We understand that each country has its histories, values, and cultures that inform what is acceptable and tolerable. In discussing the Bill before parliament, it is important, therefore, not to forget the sovereignty and peculiarity of our own nation - its culture, customs, laws, and history.

¹⁴ Reported by James Factora (October 4, 2021) at <https://www.them.us/story/canadian-court-rules-misgendering-human-rights-violation> (Accessed on October 7, 2021).

¹⁵ <https://www.thestar.com/vancouver/2019/03/12/misgendering-kids-and-preventing-transitioning-can-constitute-child-abuse-following-bc-supreme-court-ruling.html> (Accessed October 7, 2021).

¹⁶ <https://www.nbcnews.com/feature/nbc-out/teacher-leave-after-speaking-out-against-pronoun-policy-students-n1269212> (Accessed on October 7, 2021).

As is typical with many African countries, Ghana is a very religious country. It would not be an overstatement to say that religion permeates all aspects of Ghanaian life so fully – determining practically every aspect of life, including moral behavior. According to the renowned Ghanaian professor of philosophy, Kwame Gyekye (2003:3), ‘African heritage is intensely religious. The African lives in a religious univers: all actions and thoughts have a religious meaning and are inspired or influenced by a religious point of view’.¹⁷ This is

Reverend Professor John Mary Waliggo, who served as General Secretary of the Uganda Constitutional Commission in the 1990s and later became a member of the Ugandan Human Rights Commission, defines culture as “*the sum total of the values a particular society cherishes and by which its members want to identify themselves and be identified by others*”. According to him, these common values include, among others: history and language; rites, rituals and ceremonies; wisdom, philosophy and worldview; religious beliefs and morality; ancestors and leaders; signs and symbols; institutions of family, clan and society as a whole; law, the legal system and the indigenous skills and technologies; education and leadership (Waliggo, 2005:1)¹⁸.

In his paper, Professor Waliggo further defines law, following Curzon’s Dictionary definition of Law, as “the written or unwritten body of rules largely derived from custom and formal enactment which are recognized as binding among those persons who constitute a community or state, so that they shall be imposed upon and enforced among those persons as appropriate sanctions” (Waliggo, 2005:1).

The term “public morality” concerns ‘the total set of ethical-moral, legal- human rights values, customs or traditions which define, describe, promote and defend a given society’s or community’s common good, shared values and vision, their public ethos, and the common pursuit of the good in order to achieve their full potential and civilization” (Waliggo, 2005:1).

From the above definitions, it is clear that both the law and public morality are expected to regulate the relationship among individuals and between individuals and the community or the State. Morality also deals with the way an individual should conduct himself or herself in the community. Public morality and the law, therefore, should more or less play the same role in society and one ought to be intrinsically integrated within other, thus creating the necessary harmony (Waliggo, 2005:2).

As Professor Waliggo opines, often times, the law seems to be divorced from public morality. In the Common law tradition, the law seems to concentrate on minimizing the harm that an individual may cause to another individual, while paying less attention on the harm done by the individual to the community as a whole and to the future of that community or state. Contemporary law in Africa, in following that

¹⁷ Kwame Gyekye (2003:3). African Cultural Values: An Introduction. Sankofa Publishing Company, Accra, Ghana.

¹⁸ John M. Waliggo (2005:1). Law and Public Morality in Africa: Legal, Philosophical and Cultural Values. Unpublished Conference Paper.

tradition, is perceived as primarily protecting the individual and his or her private interests rather than equally emphasizing the protection of the good of all in the society or community (Waliggo, 2005:2).

In the Common law tradition, as it pertains to the western nations now, the law seems to trump culture and public morality. However, in Africa, public morality is based on a strong sense of shame for the individual who acts or behaves contrary to the common good of the community and its values. This is founded on the philosophy: “We are and therefore I am” (Waliggo, 2005:2). Thus, African cultures emphasize morality more than the laws. Moral formation in Africa is passed on to children right from the tender age to enable him or her to fit into the community. An individual lived in and was part of the community and it was everyone’s duty to uphold the community’s values. In Africa, morality is understood as law in a sense (Waliggo, 2005:2).

In concluding his paper, Professor Waliggo recommended strongly that Africa will continue to closely relate the law with morality in general and public morality in particular in order to preserve, promote and protect the human person, the community and the future of Africa.

To Professor Robert Peter George, an American Legal Scholar and Political Philosopher, who served as the sixth McCormick Professor of Jurisprudence and Director of the James Madison Program in American Ideals and Institutions at Princeton University, public morality should be viewed in the same way we view public health and safety. He feels that ‘what is true for public health and safety is equally true for public morality’.¹⁹ Using the example of the problem of pornography, Professor George argues that “materials designed to arouse carnal sexual desire, where it is allowed to flourish, damages a community’s moral ecology in ways comparable to those in which carcinogenic smoke emitted from a factory damages a community’s physical ecology. The harm of pornography is not only that it shocks and offends people’s sensibilities but rather the central harm of pornography is moral harm - harm to character” (George, 2000:17).

Public morals are affected, for good or ill, by the activities of private parties, and such parties have obligations in respect to it. The acts of private individuals, sometimes even the apparently private acts of private persons, can and do have public consequences. And choices to do things that one knows will bring about these consequences, whether directly or indirectly are governed by moral norms, including, above all, norms of justice. Such norms will often constitute conclusive reasons for private individuals to refrain from actions that produce harmful public consequences.

For all these reasons, it will be wrong for anyone to argue that the state has no authority to proscribe homosexual acts, which by the Ghanaian culture, is an immoral sexual act, is absurd. Our rich Ghanaian tradition, history and culture, including religious attitudes, have no room for LGBTQ+ practices. Same-sex marriage is a behaviour that is opposed by the majority of Ghanaians because it is contrary to our

¹⁹ George, R.P, (2000).The Concept of Public Morality, 45 Am. J. Juris, 17(2000).

shared norms, social values, and customs. Nananom expressed concern about the Bill saying nowhere in history does the Ghanaian culture subscribe to LGBTQ+, which is “taboo, inhuman and alien to society”.

As Professor Gyekye notes in his book (page 78), “homosexuality is considered a taboo and would be outlawed on moral as well as social grounds, because the continuity of the family and, indeed, of the human species would be most seriously affected if homosexuality were practiced. Some may argue that homosexuals can still procreate through artificial insemination and the likes but Professor Gyekye rightly maintains that this artificial means of producing children, which could be used by a family composed of a homosexual couple is far removed from the ideas and practices of childbirth in the traditional African Society”.

Homosexuality is alien to our national history, culture and values. Allowing it will destroy our cultural heritage. It is heartwarming to notice that the Constitutional Review Commission noted that Ghana’s human rights are situated in the African Charter on Human and People’s Rights. This Charter provides in the preamble that human rights must take into consideration the virtues of their (The Africans) historical tradition and the values of African civilization. The Charter further says that the individual who seeks his or her human rights to be protected has the responsibility to protect the social and cultural values of the society: —the individual shall also have the duty to preserve and strengthen positive African values in his relations with other members of the society, in the spirit of tolerance, dialogue and consultation and, in general, to contribute to the promotion of the moral well-being of society. On the basis of this, the CRC was of the view that homosexuality could, arguably, be an example of a situation where the desire of an individual to have sex with a person of the same sex should not be recognised as long as that practice fails to sit with the socio-cultural values of the society in which the individual finds himself.

5. Public Health Concerns

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development defines a set of ambitious global health goals and targets. Of particular interest to the matter at hand is Goal 3: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages, including its focus on health-related areas.

While many of the issues surrounding sexual orientation and gender identity remain controversial among researchers, there is general agreement on the observation that LGBTQ+ subpopulations are at higher risk, compared to the general population, of numerous health problems. Professors Mayer and McHugh examine research on health outcomes as they relate to sexual orientation and gender identity and provided the following conclusion: “Compared to the general population, non-heterosexual and transgender subpopulations have higher rates of mental health problems such as anxiety, depression, and suicide, as well as behavioral and social problems such as substance abuse and intimate partner violence” (Mayer & McHugh, 2016:59). They observed a consistently higher risk of poor physical and mental health outcomes for lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender subpopulations compared to the general population. These outcomes include depression, anxiety, substance abuse, and most alarmingly, suicide. For example, among the transgender subpopulation in the United States, the rate of attempted suicide is estimated to be as high

as 41%, ten times higher than in the general population. As physicians, academics, and scientists, we believe all of the subsequent discussions in this report must be cast in the light of this public health issue. Compared to the general population, adults who have undergone sex-reassignment surgery continue to have a higher risk of experiencing poor mental health outcomes. One study found that, compared to controls, sex-reassigned individuals were about 5 times more likely to attempt suicide and about 19 times more likely to die by suicide.

In a 2008 meta-analysis of research on mental health outcomes for non-heterosexuals, University College London professor of psychiatry Michael King and colleagues²⁰ concluded that gays, lesbians, and bisexuals face “higher risk of suicidal behaviour, mental disorder and substance misuse and dependence than heterosexual people” (King et al., 2008, cited in Mayer and McHugh, 2016:60). Compiling the risk ratios found in these papers, the authors estimated that lesbian, gay, and bisexual individuals had a 2.47 times higher life-time risk than heterosexuals for suicide attempts, that they were about twice as likely to experience depression over a twelve-month period, and approximately 1.5 times as likely to experience anxiety disorders. Both non-heterosexual men and women were found to be at an elevated risk for substance abuse problems (1.51 times as likely), with the risk for non-heterosexual women especially high—3.42 times higher than for heterosexual women. Non-heterosexual men, on the other hand, were at a particularly high risk for suicide attempts: while non-heterosexual men and women together were at a 2.47 times greater risk of suicide attempts over their lifetimes, non-heterosexual men were found to be at a 4.28 times greater risk. Combined worldwide studies showed up to 50% higher rates of mental disorders and substance abuse among persons self-identifying in surveys as lesbian, gay, or bisexual. Lesbian or bisexual women showed higher levels of substance abuse, while gay or bisexual men had higher rates of depression and panic disorder.

The LGBTQ+ advocates have tried to minimize these serious observations with the explanation that social stressors such as stigmatization and discrimination faced by members of their community account for the disparity in mental health outcomes. These efforts have succeeded in the passing of anti-discrimination and hate-crime laws in some jurisdictions but these strategies have not been able to eliminate all of the disparities in mental health outcomes between the LGBTQ+ subpopulation and the wider population. According to professors Mayer and McHugh, other factors, such as the elevated rates of sexual abuse victimization among the LGBTQ+ population may also account for some of these mental health disparities, as research has consistently shown that survivors of childhood sexual abuse are significantly at risk of a wide range of medical, psychological, behavioral, and sexual disorders.

²⁰ Michael King et al., “A systematic review of mental disorder, suicide, and deliberate self-harm in lesbian, gay and bisexual people,” *BMC Psychiatry* 8 (2008): 70, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-8-70>.

Homosexual Partnerships and the HIV/AIDS Pandemic

HIV/AIDS is a major concern, not just from the perspective of public health in valuing individual health and human rights, but also from a development standpoint in terms of its role in diminishing the labor force. There is already a lot of literature on this subject – the correlation between homosexual acts and HIV/AIDS – so I would not want to bore you by mere repetitions of what is already common knowledge.

It is common knowledge that HIV/AIDS, as a global phenomenon, is frequently associated with homosexual partnerships. Both the degree of promiscuity and the nature of homosexual practice mean the gay men are at risk of contracting all kinds of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and especially AIDS, as well as hepatitis, rectal cancer, non-viral and viral infections and a decrease in life expectancy. In the early 1980s, AIDS was called “the gay plague” precisely because it seemed to hit the gay subpopulation hardest.

According to the UNAIDS’ own report, same-sex relationship, anal sex especially, carries a high risk of transmission of HIV. According to the report, “sex between men is the main route of transmission of HIV in some parts of the world. In some other places it is a secondary route of transmission. Nearly everywhere, it is a significant and interconnected part of the epidemic and needs to be taken seriously into consideration.” (UNAIDS, 1998:2).²¹ The report further revealed that about 5-10% of all HIV infections worldwide are due to sexual contact between men, with some considerable variation across countries and places. In North America, parts of Latin America, most of Europe, Australia and New Zealand, the rates are often as high as 70%.

6. Economic Arguments

The Social and Economic Implications Homosexuality

There are several mechanisms by which same-sex relationships could affect macroeconomic performance. The most notorious among the channels is through sexual health-related challenges surrounding homosexual acts. It is an already established fact that same-sex relationships, anal sex especially, carries a high risk of transmission of sexually transmitted infections, including the human immunodeficiency virus, which causes AIDS (UNAIDS, 1998). In Africa, HIV/AIDS has had a significant effect on multiple sectors of the economy, including health (through dramatic increases in people seeking care; expensive treatment of HIV-related illnesses; pressure overwhelming health systems), education (through reduced supply of teachers; school dropouts) and agriculture (through loss of labour supply and remittance income).

The International Labour Office of the United Nations (ILO) released a soul-searching report in 2000 entitled: HIV/AIDS: A threat to decent work, productivity and development. In this document, prepared

²¹ UNAIDS (1998). AIDS and Men who have Sex with Men. UNAIDS Point of View. July 1998.

for discussion at the Special High-Level Meeting on HIV/AIDS and the World of Work in Geneva, made some telling revelations on the socio-economic implications of HIV/AIDS (ILO, 2000:12):²²

- AIDS deaths lead directly to a reduction in the number of workers available, and particularly workers in their most productive years. As experienced workers are replaced by younger, less experienced persons, productivity is reduced.
- A shortage of skilled workers leads to higher production costs and a loss of international competitiveness.
- Lower government revenues and reduced private savings (because of greater health care costs and a loss of income for workers) can lead to slower employment creation in the formal sector, which is particularly capital intensive. As a result, some workers will be pushed into lower paying jobs in the informal sector.
- Expenditure increases on the monitoring of high-risk groups, the establishment of prevention strategies, the provision of health care and welfare.
- Pressure increases on the social security system, including life insurance and pension funds, which are important sources of capital for both the government and the private sector.

The ILO reported that studies had shown that HIV/AIDS reduced the rate of economic growth by as much as 25 per cent over a 20-year period in Tanzania, Cameroon, Zambia, Swaziland, Kenya and other sub-Saharan African countries. In Botswana, Namibia, South Africa, Zambia and Zimbabwe, the life expectancy at birth in 2000-2005 was expected to be between 20 and 29 years lower than it would have been in the absence of AIDS, and their populations are expected to be up to 20 per cent smaller than they would have been by 2015.

These awful effects of the scourge of AIDS in Africa amply demonstrates that, when a culture departs from God's standard, frightful consequences are to be expected. Unfortunately, both the wicked and the innocent suffer the consequences alike. It is therefore essential to the health and welfare of all Ghanaians that we be governed by God's Holy Word. We must take the Bible seriously and campaign for the restoration and preservation of moral constraint laws, including the instant anti-LGBTQ+ Bill before the honourable members of parliament.

Private and Public Roles and Responsibilities

Rational choice is central to the economic view of behavior. Today's society places a high value on personal choice. Our society generally accepts that allowing individuals to make their own choices raises their sense of well-being, higher than it would be if such choices were made by a well-intentioned central planner. The case for public interventions in individual decisions and choices, however, is quite strong. Smoking is one of such lifestyle choices about which most people today agree that there is need for government intervention. Today, no one debates the conclusion that smoking is harmful to one's health, not even smokers. Tobacco is major public health problem. It is a personal health problem but it affects nearly all of us in some way. However, cigarette and other tobacco products do provide some form of pleasure to those who consume them. In the late 19th century, smoking was widely viewed as morally wrong, offensive, harmful to health and contrary to the value of thrift. Another reason for government

²² ILO (2000). HIV/AIDS: A threat to decent work, productivity and development. Geneva.

intervention against smoking is the belief that people do not have sufficient knowledge to make an informed decision about tobacco use. Tobacco manufacturers are alleged to have misinformed the public about the risks of smoking through their advertising campaigns. Young persons may be particularly vulnerable to such misinformation and therefore may underestimate their personal risk. The government has a duty in regulating the flow of such information and to control the individual choices. Similarly, the fact that same-sex relationships allow people to achieve some gains (which some might call happiness) does not automatically mean that it should be allowed.

There are situations in which market outcomes are not socially optimal or desirable, popularly known in economics as market failure. Market failure may be due to the existence of market power, imperfect information, public goods, or externalities. The marriage market is no different. Marriage has major implications for, among other things, the fertility rate and the population growth, the labour force participation for women, sexual health-related issues - sexual orientation and gender identity, sexual expression, and relationships, including their negative consequences or conditions such as infections with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and reproductive tract infections (RTIs) and their adverse outcomes (such as cancer and infertility); and unintended pregnancy and abortion.

The basic worldview of neoclassical economists is that free markets make people better off, depending on many (often unspoken) assumptions, including rationality, perfect information and self-interest. The assumption of rationality means that individuals must act in ways that further their objectives. The assumption of self-interest means decisions must only take into account benefits and costs to themselves. Their actions must not affect any “third parties”. The assumption of perfect information suggests that in making decisions, they must possess perfect information about all factors (past, present, and future) that could affect their decisions.

However, markets sometimes fail, including marriage. When a mining company pollutes the rivers and streams, people suffer a cost. The “Galamsey” menace is a case in point. In cases like this, the unregulated pursuit of self-interest leads to outcomes that are *Pareto* inefficient. One solution is for the government to step in with regulations that ban mining companies from the imposition of pollution costs on others. To decide to what extent the government should step in, economists propose cost-benefit analysis in weighing the costs against the benefits. In the same vein, the invitation to the state to strengthen the laws that regulate this all-important marriage market, especially as it pertains to homosexual relationships, could not be said to be out of place in a progressive society. Irrationality (especially among the youthful and uninitiated population), imperfect information about all relevant factors and potential benefits and costs, self-interest, market power imbalances (especially regarding income, age and racial inequities), and potential negative externalities, would justify social institutions, including the state, to lawfully control this marriage market.

Is Homosexuality a Free and Rational Choice?

The issue of preference in economics – free choice – is predicated on the assumption of rationality, *Ceteris Paribus*, that human beings are rational. But we know that not all human beings are rational or think rationally all the time. It is therefore the duty of the state to curtail any irrational behaviours of any individuals for the common good. This is why in progressive societies, states have laws to curtail monopoly power and anticompetitive behaviours of capitalist private enterprises. That is why there are standards authorities to regulate what is wholesome. As long as the monopolist is allowed to decide on what to produce, when to produce, how much to produce and what price to charge for the products, there will be a market disequilibrium and there is no way this will result in better service for the public. The monopolist, if allowed his freedom, will be making large excess profits at the expense of the general public's welfare. These situations require government regulation or antitrust policies. The economic rationale for regulation is that there is some identifiable market failure considered to be so great that intervention to correct it will be efficient, in the sense that the costs of the intervention will be lower than the costs of the failure.

Take, for example, the recent global financial crises of 2007-09 and our own recent local banking crisis in Ghana and the fact that it was the private inordinate desire for wealth and unchecked irresponsible, reckless, and risky conducts of certain private individuals that brought us there. Remember the amount of hard earned Ghanaian tax payers money that had to be injected into saving and reviving the financial sector. Remember the jobs lost, lives lost, families broken, etc. How on earth could anyone say that what individual bank CEOs do is none of our business? As we have seen recently in Ghana, the failure of one bank could lead to the failure of others, and ultimately to a loss of confidence in the financial system as a whole. The failure of an individual bank can trigger systemic crises and typically disrupt a whole financial system, leading to reduced lending, investment and a decline in the overall level of economic activity. This form of market failure create the need for the regulation of individual banks. That is why the Bank of Ghana has withdrawn the licenses of a number of financial institutions. It is for the public good. Such regulations seek to promote the efficiency of banks and protect consumers. In fact, stricter regulation and supervision of the banking industry often follows a financial crisis.

Concern for future generations motivates environmental law. The concept of sustainable development requires a non-decreasing utility over time. The private actions of individual persons, including homosexuals, that would jeopardize the existence of Ghana as a 'going concern' must be legally controlled. Contrary to what others say, there is such a thing as right and wrong, pure and impure, honourable and dishonourable, virtue and vice, good and evil, worthy and unworthy, wholesome and unwholesome, moral and immoral, righteousness and sin. Why do we have Standards Board, including the Food and Drug Agency, to certify and approve what is wholesome, what is convenient? Imagine for a moment, if a producer says that he has the right to produce whatever he desires without regard to wholesomeness and standards, what would you think of him or her? Our liberties must be guided according to commonly accepted standards.

Is There a Relationship Between Economic Development and LGBTQ+ Acceptance?

It is worth considering whether there is any relationship between economic development, income and legalization of homosexuality. Let us consider an example with automobile insurance. Suppose that you have just purchased a brand new vehicle with full security installations and purchased a comprehensive insurance policy that completely reimburses you for any damage that your car suffers as a result of an accident. Now that you know that you have a brand new car and are fully insured, how careful will you be? Perhaps not as careful as you would have been if you were driving a second-hand car without insurance. Perhaps, you will drive faster, or behave more recklessly under adverse weather conditions. This example illustrates the concept of moral hazard in economics, the phenomenon whereby an insured party exercises less care than he or she would in the absence of insurance. What is the application to the LGBTQ+ issue? The citizens of industrialized countries know that they have the best of healthcare facilities and the best trained health care personnel. They also know that they have very generous social insurance systems, like the UK NHIS. How careful do you expect the citizens to behave? Compare the personal and public health attitudes of individuals who are fully vaccinated against COVID-19 (or countries that have vaccinated almost all their citizens) and individuals who have not yet received a single dose of the vaccine. Which of these two groups of individuals (or countries) would take more precaution? We know in economics that consumption and lifestyle patterns differ markedly between the rich and the poor, developed and developing economies.

Tables 2-4 shows the clear disparities between Ghana and five selected developed economies, where LGBTQ+ rights have been legalized. It is obvious that these countries are not our *equal equal*, by any of the selected metrics. For example, the annual per capita health spending in America is more than \$10,000, compared with just \$18 per year in Ghana. You can just imagine what GHC 100 can do in terms of health care expenditure for an LGBTQ+ Ghanaian. The GDP per capita of Denmark in 2020 was more than 63,000, compared with Ghana's \$1,848. This means that the average Dane is almost 35 times richer and more resourceful than his/her Ghanaian counterpart. In terms of life expectancy, the average Australian lives almost 20 years longer than the average Ghanaian. Furthermore, the poverty headcount ratio indicate that more than half of the Ghanaian population are poor, living on less than \$5.50 (equivalent of about GHC 30 today) a day at 2011 international prices. From the foregoing stark realities, it would be awkward to expect that individuals living in these two separate worlds to be allowed to make the same lifestyle choices.

Table 2: GDP Per Capita and Health Outcomes

Country	Year	GDP per capita (constant 2010 US\$)	Mortality rate, infant (per 1,000 live births)	Life Expectancy
Ghana				
	1960	1,057	128.9	45.6
	2007	1,135	55.2	59.6
	2020	1,848	33.7	64.2
Denmark				
	1960	20,538	22.0	72.2
	2007	61,175	3.9	78.3
	2020	63,880	3.0	81.0
Netherlands				
	1960	16,387	17.2	73.1
	2007	51,809	4.3	79.9
	2020	53,081	2.4	82.3
UK				
	1960	13,949	23.2	70.8
	2007	41,462	4.9	79.4
	2020	39,103	3.6	81.4
USA				
	1960	17,578	26.4	69.8
	2007	49,856	6.8	78.0
	2020	53,749	5.7	78.9
Australia				
	1960	19,378	20.6	70.6
	2007	51,024	4.5	81.3
	2020	56,307	3.0	83.5

Source: Macrotrends (life-expectancy & mortality series); World Bank (GDP per capita series)

Table 3: Health Spending Per Capita

Country	Year	Health Spending Per Capita (US \$)
Ghana	2000	18
	2018	78
Denmark	2000	2,496
	2018	6,217
Netherlands	2000	2,028
	2018	5,307
UK	2000	2,054
	2018	4,315
USA	2000	4,564
	2018	10,624
Australia	2000	1,639
	2018	5,425

Source: WDI, World Bank

Table 4: Poverty Rate

Country	Year	Poverty at \$5.50 a day
Ghana	2005	75.9
	2016	55.1
Denmark	2005	0.5
	2016	0.4
Netherlands	2005	0.4
	2016	0.3
UK	2005	1.2
	2016	0.5
USA	2005	1.5
	2016	1.7
Australia	2001	1.3
	2008	0.7
	2014	0.7

Source: WDI, World Bank

Mmobrowa Ghanaians, struggling to make ends meet, cannot afford to emulate the same expensive lifestyles we see in the rich and developed countries. Over the last several decades, the developed countries have invested in institutions and both social and physical infrastructure to be able to contain some of the negative effects emanating from the legalization of same-sex marriages and the liberties and rights accorded the LGBTQ+ community. As a nation, we should learn from our history and present realities and make the right policy choices. The scourge of the HIV/AIDS and its devastating effect of the African continent should not be lost on us this soon. A lot of the human capital of Africa was decimated by this HIV/AIDS epidemic, especially the youths. A number of countries in Sub Sahara Africa are yet to recover fully from this plague. We should also take a cue from the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and the inequities in access to vaccines. COVID-19 has exposed several vulnerabilities in our country and should serve as a warning to thread cautiously. King Solomon once asked: “Can a man carry fire next to his chest and his clothes not be burned? Or can one walk on hot coals and his feet not be scorched?” (Proverbs 6:27-28). I believe you know the right answer. “Asem bone se ohiani ba, nti me dee medwene me ho”. The following Twi maxims may be apt to describe what I am trying to communicate here.

“Dee ofira ntomago no, onni mpipiragoro”.

“Aserewa hwe ne keseɛ ansa na wanwono ne pirebuo”.

“Se wote ahwewhedan mu a, ntoto aboo”.

7. The Biblical Case against Homosexuality

Last but certainly not the least, let us consider religious arguments why the LGBTQ+ movement must not be countenanced in Ghana.

Why do the nations plan rebellion? Why do people make their useless plots? Their kings revolt, their rulers plot together against the Lord and against the king he chose.

*“Let us free ourselves from their rule,” they say;
“let us throw off their control.” – Psalm 2:1-3*

*Woe unto them that call evil good, and good evil;
that put darkness for light, and light for darkness;
that put bitter for sweet, and sweet for bitter! – Isa. 5:20*

*Even as I have seen, they that plow iniquity,
and sow wickedness, reap the same. – Job 4:8*

The Holy Bible is unambiguous on the issue of homosexuality. According to Scripture, homosexuality is, first of all, an act of unbelief (Romans 1:18). The broader context of biblical injunctions against homosexuality is that it constitutes a manifest rebellion against God’s sovereignty and His intention in

creation, and a gross perversion of His good and perfect plan for His created order. Homosexuality is therefore an assault upon the integrity of creation and God’s intention in creating human beings in two distinct and complementary genders.

Age of Enlightenment

The Enlightenment was a movement in the European thought which began the modern era. This movement began in France in the early 1700s and spread from there to England and Germany and eventually to America. The Enlightenment philosophers rejected not only the Bible, but all of theology as well (Hindson and Caner, 2008). Their motive was to inaugurate a new era in thought that would radically change the culture of the world. The Enlightenment engendered many beliefs that are still popular today. Among these are the ideas related to freedom – of thought, speech, religion, and the press. The proponents believed that human beings are by nature good and rational and will by nature gravitate toward what is true. They argued that human minds, no longer “shackled” by the superstitions of religion, would usher in a new age of truth and freedom for everyone. This is totally unscriptural – man is naturally fallen and sinful, not good. Left to himself, man will not choose good (Job 15:4; Ps. 58:3; Ps. 51:5).

For I know that nothing good lives in me, that is, in my flesh [my human nature, my worldliness—my sinful capacity]. For the willingness [to do good] is present in me, but the doing of good is not – Romans 7:18.

While the Enlightenment movement brought about some positive developments, including modern democracies and universal education, it introduced a new age of *secularism*. It assumed that religious beliefs, because it cannot be proven clearly and distinctly by sight, must be rejected on the basis of the principle of doubt. This kind of ideology has led to a secular world that challenges the priority given to religious beliefs and values. Indeed, many historians have referred to the Enlightenment as the rise of *modern paganism*.

God’s commandments have not changed. His moral injunctions have withstood the testing of time. The frustrations and defects of humanity have not relegated them to a place of irrelevancy. The commandment of God makes a nation wiser than its neighbours. It is as Moses stated:

God has taught us statutes and judgments.... We must keep therefore and do them; for this is our wisdom.... (Deut 4:5, 6).

The name of the ancient city of Sodom has become a synonym for homosexual behavior. The biblical record indicates that the mob became violent and tried to break down the door of Lot’s house. Only divine intervention spared Lot and his household from their evil intentions, and God subsequently destroyed both Sodom and the neighboring city of Gomorrah (Genesis 19:4–11, 24–25). God’s punishment of these cities was of such severity that it is used as an illustration of divine judgment by both Peter (2 Peter 2:6) and Jude (7). Jude’s commentary on homosexuality is particularly fitting for our times, “In a similar way,

Sodom and Gomorrah and the surrounding towns gave themselves up to sexual immorality and perversion. They serve as an example of those who suffer the punishment of eternal fire.”

It is important to note that wherever homosexuality occurs in the biblical record it is an occasion of scandal and judgment. Homosexual acts are never viewed in a positive light in scripture. These are provocations to the eyes of God’s glory (Isaiah 3:8-9). Anybody can say whatever he fancies but according to the old book, homosexuality is a sickness - of the soul, of the heart, and of the mind (Romans 1:18). Sin is the sickness of the soul; only pardoning mercy heals and renewing grace can heal it, and for this spiritual healing we should be more earnest than for bodily health. I thought the scourge of HIV/AIDS was going to reduce reckless sexual immorality but it did not. We have invented anti-retroviral drugs and this has emboldened people to be more reckless. I know that no amount of fiat or criminal/penal codes/law can eradicate same-sex relationships. The Bible already prophetically predicted this sort of misbehavior in the times in which we live. But wrong is wrong and sin is sin.

We live in days when there is a mighty zeal for education and knowledge. Knowledge shall abound. We here of new inventions and innovations, and scientific discoveries. And still, the vast majority of people die younger than in the medieval times. There are much more epidemics and pandemics, global and local crisis and everywhere. We are not healthier than our great grandparents. Life expectancy has been cut short globally. What accounts for this state of things? The plain truth is that the God’s commandments are not regarded.

Years should teach wisdom, but sometimes the aged do not learn. Our elders say ‘*Gray hair does not necessarily indicate gray matter*’. ‘*Antiquity is no help against stupidity*’ (Martin Luther). I have, sometimes, been perfectly astonished of eminent and highly educated citizens who fail to admit that LGBTQ+ practices are wrong. Remember, human beings are born with a decided bias towards evil so if you let them choose they are likely to choose evil. That’s why child training is necessary. “Foolishness is bound in the heart of a child (Prov. 22:15). “A child left to himself bringeth his mother to shame” (Prov. 29:15). For goodness sake we should not abandon people to their own wayward tastes and inclinations. Their pleasures and wishes must not be allowed to guide their actions. Otherwise, why do we need speed limits and traffic laws and regulations. Some drivers like to drive at 180 mph in town, others still wish to drive on the opposite side of the road. Should they be allowed to do so? Is it their human right to drive anyway, anywhere and anyhow? Obviously not.

8. Conclusion and Policy Options

Let us allow reason and common sense to prevail. Every waking moment of our lives, we operate from one of two viewpoints: human or divine. We often jealously guard our autonomy from heaven and much prefer to think and conduct our lives independent of our Maker. Consequently, human opinions influence us more than God’s commands and principles. We base our choices on what is best for ourselves without much regard for the long-term moral implications. Human solutions give us the illusion of greater security and pleasure, so we tend to either reject or ignore divine injunctions and remedies.

Like Ghana today, America was once a very religious nation with many Americans professing to be Christians. America's first two presidents, George Washington and John Adams, were firm believers in the importance of religion for republican government. In his Farewell Address, president Washington advised the nation that religion and morality (virtue or morality), were the great pillars of human happiness and a necessary spring of popular governments.

“Of all the dispositions and habits which lead to political prosperity, religion and morality are indispensable supports. In vain would that man claim the tribute of patriotism, who should labor to subvert these great pillars of human happiness, these firmest props of the duties of men and citizens. The mere politician, equally with the pious man, ought to respect and to cherish them.”
-- President George Washington.

Noah Webster Jr., an American lexicographer, textbook pioneer, reformer and political writer, who was referred to as the “Father of American Scholarship and Education”, once admonished his fellow citizens that; “God commands you to choose for rulers just men who will rule in the fear of God. The preservation of a republican government depends on the faithful discharge of this duty; if the citizens neglect their duty and place unprincipled men in office, the government will soon be corrupted; laws will be made, not for the public good, so much as for the selfish or local purposes; corrupt or incompetent men will be appointed to execute the laws; the public revenues will be squandered on unworthy men; and the rights of the citizens will be violated or disregarded.”

Unfortunately, Mr. Webster's counsel was not fully heeded to. Over the years, immoral men and women, who had no fear of God before their eyes, were elected or appointed into political offices, who enacted and passed unrighteous laws, not for the public good, but so much as for the selfish interests. Worse still, corrupt and unprincipled men were appointed to adjudicate or execute the unwholesome laws. The consequence is a new America, which is fast falling from grace to grass. Just a few weeks ago Gallup released polling data showing that less than 50 percent of Americans report belonging to a faith community. Back in 1970, when Gallup first began tracking this data, more than 70 percent of Americans belonged to religious communities.²³ It is not surprising that America is not bleeding with crime, violence, racial discrimination, sexual perversions and all sorts of immoralities, and legal tussles of gay and human rights. The battle over LGBTQ+ rights is being fought in nearly every corner of American society — from public schools to the highest courts. For example, in countries where homosexuality is legalized, citizens who dislike homosexuality are forced to accept them or lose their jobs or their businesses would be closed down. Homosexual rights now trump religious rights and freedom of conscience in many western societies. Lawyers were in a U.S Fifth Circuit Court of Appeal recently arguing against federal mandates that would violate conscience rights and force hospitals and doctors to perform gender-transition surgeries, including on minors, against their religious beliefs.

²³ <https://news.gallup.com/poll/341963/church-membership-falls-below-majority-first-time.aspx> (Accessed on October 7, 2021).

Dear Honourable Parliamentarians, permit me to now address you directly. The nation has placed its destiny into your hands. Our prayers are with you. Be ye strong and courageous and do the needful, and let not your hands be weak: for your work shall be rewarded. Posterity will appreciate you for the single act of preserving a sound moral ecology for our children and grandchildren.

Almighty God, Creator of the universe, who has given us this good land for our heritage, we humbly entreat You that we may always prove ourselves a people mindful of your blessings and glad to do Your will. Please give our honourable MPs, the power to discern clearly right from wrong, and allow all their words and actions to be governed thereby, and by the Scriptures. By Thy grace, and by the righteousness of our cause, we shall triumph over evil. With Thy blessing, we shall prevail over the unholy forces of evil.

God bless our homeland Ghana.

God bless you.

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

October 7, 2021

Legon, Accra.